

VALKYRIES

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1. Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to detail the proceedings of the Task 7.8, resulting in the implementation of a demonstration based on Use Case (UC) 4 – CROSS-BORDER RESPONSE TO THE DISASTER CONTAINING THE SPREADING OF TOXIC SUBSTANCE OF POLLUTION ON SEA IN INTERNATIONAL WATERS(NORWAY-SWEDEEN-DENMARK).

The UC4 scenario establishes the conditions for a multi-casualty incident (MCI) in a maritime environment, with the emergency situation posing a cross-border threat. This emphasizes the necessity for multiple responding units to work collaboratively during the response phase, making the exercise both multi-agency and cross-border in its orientation.

This deliverable describes the results from the harmonisation opportunities identified in the WP4 that have been tested in the UC4. In particular, the UC4 demonstrated the integration of advanced technologies such as drones and body cameras within the VALKYRIES platform.

Based on feedback from the participants involved in the exercise, UC4 was considered highly successful, and the VALKYRIES solutions introduced were well-received. This success emphasizes the ability of project to effectively address cross-border emergency response scenarios and leverage advanced technologies to improve emergency response capabilities in maritime environments.

Figure 1 - Valkyries Use Cases

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Report of the use case: Norway-Sweden-Denmark

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Name of Contributors: All partners

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Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. This document describes the outcomes achieved when testing the VALKYRIES solutions in a real demonstration between Norway, Sweden and Denmark, as well as outlining the impact of the demonstration outcomes and end-user acceptance.

3. Introduction

The VALKYRIES project focuses on evaluating the present status of protocols, nomenclatures, technologies, and procedures in use by European first responders. The objective is to propose a series of pre-standardization and harmonization actions, enabling them to collaborate effectively in cross-border incidents. The project consortium suggests various pre-standardization and harmonization initiatives to ensure that First Responders (FRs) can function effectively in Multi-Casualty Cross-border incidents (MCI). These harmonization proposals are applied within a reference integration platform named SIGRUN. The effectiveness of these proposals was verified and showcased in UC4.

With aim to prepare and implement the demonstrations (exercises) optimally standardized process was agreed between the related partners and all the steps was captured in document called EXSPEC (Exercise Specification, respectively DEMSPEC-Demonstration Specification). It was the crucial document for preparation and implementation of the demonstration. Goal of this document was to summarize and prepare all the information related to demonstrations of stated UCs and necessary to implement them in effective manner with aim to present VALKYRIES elements on a relatively simple case before moving on to an extensive deployment. Data from this document are used here.

3.1. Justification

During the initial phase of the VALKYRIES project, end-user's needs were identified in multi-casualty incidents (MCI), which led to the formulation of a specific set of requirements. In the following stage, various technological tools, systems, and equipment were recommended, along with operational procedures, common practices, and enhancements to the training and education system. Subsequently opportunities for harmonization and standardization were developed. The outcomes of this initiative are being assessed and validated through four use cases, including UC4. A more detailed description of the tested technological tools and opportunities is provided in chapter 9.

3.2. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.8_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D7.8	REQUIRED	Attended as observers Norway-Sweden-Denmark exercise, Lysekil, 2022
REQ_BASE_T7.8_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6	D7.8	REQUIRED	Attended as observers other UCs and had debriefing. Lesson and learned have been reported

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.8_3	P1	VALK-OBJ1 VALK-OBJ9	D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Valkyries solutions and drone are tested in UC4 and tested one week before UC4
REQ_BASE_T7.8_4	P1	VALK-OBJ4 VALK-OBJ5 VALK-OBJ6 VALK-OBJ7 VALK-OBJ8 VALK-OBJ9	D7.8	RECOMMENDED	Based on D7.3, a survey was conducted after UC4
REQ_BASE_T7.8_5	P1	VALK-OBJ6 VALK-OBJ7 VALK-OBJ8 VALK-OBJ9	D2.8 D7.2	RECOMMENDED	Valkyries defines Minimum data set representing MCI and emergency response information
REQ_BASE_T7.8_6	P1	VALK-OBJ6 VALK-OBJ7 VALK-OBJ8 VALK-OBJ9	D7.8	RECOMMENDED	In UC4, drones collect and transmit real-time data. It can show how this data can be immediately accessed and interpreted by FRs
REQ_BASE_T7.8_7	P1	VALK-OBJ6 VALK-OBJ7 VALK-OBJ8 VALK-OBJ9	D7.8	REQUIRED	In adverse geographical conditions, drones are used both for logistics assistance as well as for search for victims in UC4
REQ_BASE_T7.8_8	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ9	D7.8	REQUIRED	As the coordinator of the exercise, Norwegian Coastal

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
					Administration and DSB(Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection) are complying applicable legal regulations
REQ_BASE_T7.8_9	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ9	D1.17	REQUIRED	The Consortium includes ethical-legal experts who oversee compliance, regulations, and standardization.

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix

4. Demonstration specification

4.1. References

This document is prepared based on the following:

- Project VALKYRIES, Number: 101020676 — Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters (Description of Action)
- Requirements stated on Description of Action (DoA) of this project related to D7.8 Report of the UC #4: Norway-Sweden-Denmark
- D7.1 Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology
- D7.2 Datasets Management and Benchmarking
- D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation
- D7.4 Reference Integration and lessons learned.
- D2.7 Definition of system requirements and demonstration use cases
- D4.6 Opportunities for harmonization in the technology landscape for first responder response in multi-casualty disasters

4.2. General data

FULL NAME:	CROSS-BORDER RESPONSE TO THE DISASTER CONTAINING THE SPREADING OF TOXIC SUBSTANCE Section of pollution on sea in international waters (Norway-Sweden-Denmark)	
NICKNAME:	UC4	
SERIAL NUMBER:	004	
LEVEL:	OPERATIONAL	
FORM:	LIVEX	
TYPE:	FX with the elements of TTX	
DATES:	26 – 27 September 2023	
AREA:	Bolærne (South-east of Tønsberg and Horten), Norway	
OFFICER SCHEDULING AND CONDUCTING THE EXERCISE	Leif Inge Magnussen, University of South-Eastern Norway (USN)	
EXERCISE DIRECTOR:	Jon Herman Ulvensøen, USN	
PLANNING OFFICER:	Fabio Augusto de Alcantara Andrade and Leif Inge Magnussen	
LOGISTIC OFFICER:	Jon Herman Ulvensøen	
EVALUATION DIRECTOR:	Meritxell Bassols Tayeda	
HOST INSTITUTION:	USN with support of Norwegian Coastal Administration	
PARTICIPANTS:	Norwegian Coast Guard Swedish Coast Guard Redningsselskapet (RS)	INDRA ISEMI AREU SUMA112 HRT USN

PARTICIPANTS:	Norwegian Coastal Administration Interkommunalt utvalg mot forurensing (IUA)	
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Table 2 – UC4 General Data

5. Overall requirements

5.1. General framework

Within the Valkyries project, UC4 represents a demonstration of cross-border cooperation, leveraging the Valkyries solutions to address complex maritime emergencies in the waters near Norway and its neighbouring countries. UC4 was conducted as a part of an annual joint exercise between Norway, Denmark, and Sweden.

This scenario is characterized by a significant maritime incident involving a large vessel and a passenger vessel, leading to an extensive Search and Rescue (SAR) operation followed by an environmental crisis due to an oil spill from the vessels, contaminating vast sea areas and threatening coastal regions.

Through UC4, we can identify the crucial roles Valkyrie's solutions play in enhancing strategies for addressing maritime disasters, particularly those involving toxic substances, ultimately minimizing potential threats to both citizens and the environment.

5.2. Relation to other demonstrations

Compared to other UCs, the Valkyries solutions was tested at sea during UC4. UC4, the last demonstration in the VALKYRIES project, was conducted in a challenging maritime environment. Although not all VALKYRIES solutions are tested here, UC4 emphasized the necessity of advanced technological integration, such as a drone and bodycam, within the VALKYRIES platform (SIGRUN). This integration not only enabled a more detailed response during the exercise but also showcased the potential for these technologies to be standardized and utilized in future cross-border emergency responses.

6. Demonstration aims and objectives

6.1. Demonstration aim

The aim is to validate and evaluate the VALKYRIES solutions and operative procedures, as well as their collaboration in case of cross-border multi casualty incidents at sea.

6.2. Demonstration objective

EO1: Plan and conduct an FSX exercise to test how well first responders work together in a sea rescue scenario.

EO2: Verify the harmonization opportunities for VALKYRIES identified in WP4, with the aim of enhancing end users' capabilities.

EO3: Distribute the project's findings and promote the application of its results within diverse organizations.

6.3. Testing objectives

TO1: Evaluate and validate the tools proposed by the VALKYRIES project under near-real maritime conditions.

TO2: Evaluate the potential for autonomous units to enhance the situational awareness of the response.

TO3: Assess the capabilities of autonomous units in identifying and communicating hazards and emergencies, including victims' locations.

TO4: Assess the efficiency of using UAVs for the rapid transportation of equipment among first responder teams.

7. Operational scenario description

The scenario is the fundamental part of the demonstration. The scenario serves as the foundation for all activities, processes and resources needed in the demonstration. To extract most value of the demonstration the scenario should reflect a real scenario as closely as possible. In UC4 the scenario is a grounding of a container ship causing an oil spill, containers and debris in the ocean.

Yearly, Norway's coastline witnesses numerous boat and ship accidents, necessitating well-coordinated rescue missions. In 2022, leisure boat accidents claimed the lives of 34 individuals¹. The most recent significant ship accident in Norway with multiple casualties happened 19th of January 2004. MS Rocknes, a large freight ship, ran aground in the archipelago just south of the city of Bergen. Moments after grounding, the vessel capsized, prompting the Norwegian rescue society (RS) to be the first responders. Tragically, due to the grounding and capsizing, 18 of the 30 crew members on board the MS Rocknes died. Onboard the vessel was 470m³ heavy oil and 70m³ of diesel, most of which was spilled into the water, resulting in heavy pollution along the coast. Approximately 45km of shoreline was heavily contaminated. Estimates indicate that between 2000 to 3000 seabirds perished due to the heavy oil spill. The cleanup operation endured for six months following the incident²³⁴.

Figure 2 - Moments after the grounding (<https://www.bt.no/nyheter/lokalt/i/31z50/har-laqt-laquorocknesraquo-bak-seq>)

¹ Norwegian Maritim Authority (2023) <https://www.sdir.no/globalassets/arsrapport---dodsulykker-med-fritidsfartoy-2022.pdf?t=1675259458233?t=1675331567399>

² https://snl.no/MS_Rocknes

³ https://no.wikipedia.org/wiki/MS_%C2%ABRocknes%C2%BB#cite_note-5

⁴ <https://kommunikasjon.ntb.no/pressemelding/3563305/forliset-vi-aldri-glemmer?publisherId=89422>

Figure 3 - MS Rocknes capsized (<https://www.ba.no/bilder/se-bildene-rocknes-ulykken/g/1-41-851447>)

Figure 4 - Oil spill clean-up operation (<https://www.ba.no/bilder/se-bildene-rocknes-ulykken/g/1-41-851447>)

SCENARIO OF UC4:

On the evening of September 26th, a large container ship grounds just south of Fredrikstad, near the Swedish border. The grounding site is highlighted as "1" in the picture below. Following this incident, the crew on board the cargo ship promptly contacted the Joint Rescue Coordination Center (JRCC) for assistance. The JRCC swiftly coordinated a rescue mission to aid the crew members onboard the stranded vessel. Using a helicopter, the crew members are airlifted from the ship and transported to the nearest hospital. Fortunately, the crew members' injuries are minor, and they are discharged from the hospital on the same night.

At the time of the grounding the cargo ship carries 200m³ of heavy oil and 150 cargo containers. Most of the heavy oil is spilled into the water, while 20 cargo containers float in the water. The JRCC then contacts the Norwegian Coastal Administration, responsible for oil spill cleanup in Norway. The Coastal Administration immediately initiated efforts to organize the oil spill cleanup, mobilizing their resources. Given the severity of the oil spill, additional resources are

necessary. The Coastal Administration reach out to their counterparts in Sweden and Denmark. Collaboratively, the Swedish and Danish assets sailed to the oil spill area and began the oil spill cleanup alongside their Norwegian partners.

Due to weather conditions and sea currents, the oil spill is moving northwest along the Oslo Fjord. At daybreak on September 27th, reports from the shoreline described the presence of oil spill and floating containers in the Tønsberg archipelago, situated on the opposite side of the Oslo Fjord from where the grounding had occurred.

In the early morning of September 27th, a leisure boat traveling from Tønsberg to Horten collided with a submerged cargo container obscured by the oil spill. This collision took place near the island of Østre Bolærne, marked as "2" in the provided image. The impact with the floating container resulted in several individuals ending up in the water. One person on the boat made a distress call on channel 16 (Ch16) and reported a mayday message. The JRCC promptly transmitted the distress messages to all first responders and ships in the area. The Horten Rescue Society immediately dispatches boats and personnel.

Due to the circumstances, including the speed of the leisure boat at the time of impact and the prevailing weather conditions, there was an urgent need to rescue the casualties. The air temperature was reported to be 2°C, while the water temperature was 10°C. These factors, in combination with the speed of the boat at impact, raised concerns of severe injuries and the risk of hypothermia. Personnel were tasked with locating potential individuals in the water and onshore and conducting initial triage.

The leisure boat accident served as the focus for the demonstration of the Valkyries solutions.

Figure 5 - The location of the Scenario øvelse Nordisk 2023

8. Concept of the exercise (demonstration)

8.1. Phase I – Preparation

The preparation phase of the demonstration started several months prior to the demonstration. For a successful demonstration the preparation phase is an utmost important phase. A non-exhaustive list critical of actions with results is described in the table below.

Action	Details	Results
Initial coordination meetings	Meetings with the coastal administration and the rescue society. Several follow-up meetings and communication were carried out.	RS would provide one SAR boat with crew for the demonstration. The coastal administration allowed USN to observe the oil spill exercise.
Datatypes and integration	Done in iterations with assistance from consortium partners.	Various datatypes for UC 4 integrated into GobaCOP
Procurement of material for demonstration	Contact with partners in the consortium, internal at USN and external parties for procurement of various technical solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4G/5G dongles + sim cards • Tap2SOS bracelets • Drone • Body camera • Triage cards • Survival suits • Radios • Staff tracking app
Managing of transportation for entire event.	Contact with several transportation companies.	Bus for transportation, one boat for the observers and one boat for the markers.
Managing accommodation and catering	Contact with RS Noatun and the restaurant at Bolærne	Accommodation at RS Noatun, and social dinner. Lunch at Bolærne on the demonstration day
Recruit markers	Information about the demonstration was given to students at USN with the purpose to recruit them as markers at the demonstration	Contract signed with eight students

Action	Details	Results
Reconnaissance of demonstration site	One month before the demonstration to uncover the feasibility of the scenario and the technical solutions.	Minor adjustments were done to the location of the drone operation and triage location.
Dry run test	A small-scale test of the scenario and the various applications were carried out one week prior to the demonstration.	Minor adjustments were done to the timing of the scenario. Logistic operation with the drone was tested and reported.
Briefing	The day before the demonstration observers were briefed on the scenario and the applications that would be tested in the demonstration	N/A
Training	At the day of the demonstration the RS crew were trained in using the triage card.	N/A

Table 3 - Critical actions in the preparation phase

8.2. Phase II – Shaping – Technology and participants briefing.

The shaping phase encompassed two main activities:

- Briefing of participants
- Adjustment of VALKYRIES technology

A week before the demonstration, a briefing was held at RS Noatun, which brought together representatives from RS, the coastal administration, and a selection of markers. RS Noatun is the operating base of the sea rescue society (RS) in south-east Norway. During the briefing, the USN team provided a detailed description of the scenario and presented various applications. The valuable inputs and insights provided by the representatives from RS and the coastal administration played a pivotal role in further shaping the scenario.

A briefing of the observers of the demonstration was held 26th of September, one day before the demonstration, at RS Noatun. In the briefing the demonstration scenario, place of incident, distribution of forces and means as well as expected course of the action (main points) was presented. A separate part was focused on descriptions of the applications that would be demonstrated. Unfortunately, no members of the RS boat crew could attend the event, as they are all volunteers who juggle their roles with other full-time jobs.

Since UC4 would utilize no simulations (applications) a dry run of the demonstration was of utmost importance. The dry run exercise was conducted just after the briefing with RS, the costal administration, and markers. The dry run exercise was located at the premises of RS Noatun. In the dry run exercise, the scenario and all the applications, except of the Tap2SOS bracelets, was tested. The objectives of the dry run exercise were to test the feasibility of the scenario and functionality of the applications and their integration to GlobalCOP.

Used applications and solutions in UC4:

- 1 SIGRUN (reference platform)
- 2 GLOBAL COP
- 3 Staff tracking app from Particle
- 4 Tap2SOS bracelets from Aratos
- 5 Triage cards from Tassica

Other applications and tools integrated

- Autonomous drone with live streaming of video and logistics
- Body camera (GoPro)

8.3. Phase III – Conduct live exercise.

The exercise was initially scheduled to take place in Area A (Figure 6), but due to weather conditions, the oil spill drill was rescheduled to be conducted in Area B on the night of the 26th, while the triage and drone/bodycam-related exercises proceeded as planned in Area A.

Figure 6 - UC4 site location

Detailed implementation plan is presented in Table 4.

Time	Action
Oil spill scenario (26th of September)	
T0	The cargo ship ground just south of Fredrikstad, near the Norwegian-Swedish boarder.
T0+2	A mayday message is sent from the cargo ship and received by the JRCC via ch16.
T0+4	JRCC notifies ships and first responders in the area
T0+6	Multiple resources are activated and on the way to the grounded cargo ship.
T0+15	The first boat/ship arrives at the scene and reports back to the JRCC of significant oil spill and multiple cargo containers in the water.
T0+17	The JRCC contact the costal administration to report on the oil spill
T0+25	The costal administration scrambles their resources
T0+25	KV Nornen (Norwegian Coast Guard) is nominated as OSC
T0+25	A helicopter arrives at the scene and air lifts the cargo ship crew and flies them to a nearby hospital.
T0+60	The first asset from the costal administration arrives at the scene. They report of significant oil spill and the need of more resources
T0+70	The costal administration request assistance from their sister organizations in Sweden and Denmark
T0+80	Assets in Sweden and Denmark are scrambled and sails to the scene
T0+N	Assets from Norway, Sweden, and Denmark is involved in the oil clean up mission coordinated by the coastal administration.
Search and rescue mission leisure boat (27th of September)	
T0	A leisure boat crashes to a container that is submerged and occluded by the oil spill
T0+2	Emergency is reported in ch16 from the leisure boat to the JRCC
T0+10	JRCC notifies ships and first responders in the area
T0+15	RS scrambles one SAR boat from RS Noatun
T0+50	The RS vessel arrives for the rescue.
T0+55	The RS crew starts the search
T0+60	Autonomous drone is used to report location of victims (in water and in shore)
T0+80	RS (first responders) spots the victims on land
T0+110	RS makes the 1st triage (obs: also read tap2sos bands)
T0+120	One first responder brings something to the others using a drone
Simulated	
T0+150	Evacuation starts to the shore (2 nd triage) with RS boats and brings to shore

Table 4 - Time and actions during the demonstration

Further information is available in Annex B, which contains details about the UC4 implementation plan.

8.4. Phase IV – Evaluation (Brief description of the approach (algorithm and methodology) for validation and testing of the VALKYRIES results)

In the initial phase of the Valkyries project, considerable progress was made in developing the Testbeds and formulating an Evaluation Methodology, as detailed in document D7.1. This document outlines the evolution and conceptual framework of the Testbed and the system employed across four use cases in the Valkyries project. It also explains the methodology used for end users' validation of harmonization opportunities, identified within the various Work Packages of the Valkyries project.

The aim of evaluating VALKYRIES solutions in UC 4 is to thoroughly assess their functionality and usability, a critical step for leveraging the harmonization opportunities identified in WP4 and supporting first responders during cross-border maritime emergencies. This evaluation includes a comprehensive analysis, ensuring the solutions meet end user expectations and evaluating their influence on various stakeholders involved in the cross-border demonstrations.

The results and insights from the validation and evaluation processes concerning the implemented harmonisation opportunities and the VALKYRIES solutions are detailed in sections 10 and 11 of this report.

9. VALKYRIES Integrated System

The Valkyries project produced a number of harmonization proposals and developed a platform as reference integration. Validity of selected ones was demonstrated in exercise based on Use Case 4. Brief description of tools used are described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation version A/1, Annex F”.

9.1. Global Technological Schema

This is the global schema for UC4 with the tools and Command and Control configuration (Figure 7).

Figure 7 - UC4 Technological Scheme

For UC4, there were two main Headquarters, one at the Norwegian Coast Guard ship and one at the Swedish one. In each of them, the GLOBAL COP application was deployed to provide the joint operational view.

Command-and-control tools were deployed in the Field Operational Centre (FOC) on the observer's boat, where the missions were created, and where the necessary resources were assigned for the incident manually. In addition, the victims' basic personal and medical data (including triage) were registered and updated from the FOC. The GLOBAL COP was also deployed with a local view, and dashboards with real-time information on the victims were also available.

At the incident site in general, the tools used for UC4 were; SIGRUN, GLOBAL COP, Aratos Tap2SOS victim bracelets (for retrieving their basic medical data), TASSICA 3 Triage Cards (for manual victim triage), Particle's Staff Tracking mobile app (for firsthand real time update of staffs' status and position), Blockchain encryption module (this module run on background – practitioners did not realize that), and finally a body camera and a drone which transmitted video stream to GLOBAL COP, the latter with autonomous functions including automatic object detection for finding victims in the sea. In addition, live ship positions (based on their AIS-signals) were automatically collected and continuously transferred to GLOBAL COP.

10. Harmonization opportunities

10.1. WP4 harmonization opportunities

This section will provide an explanation of how the harmonisation of the opportunities assessed in UC4 has been carried out. A specific explanation of UC4 will be given.

The harmonization opportunities implemented for UC4 are the following:

- **CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles**
- **CO.WP4.28. Cross Border Data Trace**
- **CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges**
- **CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage**
- **CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs**
- **CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response**

A detailed description of each opportunity of WP4 is included in D7.3 [5].

10.1.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

This harmonized opportunity was validated in the UC4, addressing the following tests purposes:

- Validate the assets (vessels) report of their location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed;
- Validate the First Responders reported location, its updating delay and the time elapsed from the reported position until the data is displayed;

In UC4, testing was conducted in the same way as in UC3 and UC1.

10.1.2. CO.WP4.28. Cross Border Data Trace

For Cross Border data trace, the module “Blockchain logging” of the central system SIGRUN was used as in UC1 and UC3. This module records (logs) and encrypts all data and metadata exchanged between any federated or external systems connected to the SIGRUN system. Each data entry is stamped with a timestamp.

The system ensures that the logged information cannot be altered or changed, providing robust data traceability. This traceability offers maximum security and transparency for all operations, including administrative operations of the SIGRUN system, as detailed in deliverable D.5.3 titled “SIGRUN Workflow and Risk Assessment Design Document.”

Figure 8 - Mapping of the Communication

Figure 8 illustrates the systematic maritime response process during an emergency at sea, based on communications with Norwegian Maritime Authorities and other relevant participants.

In UC4, the Norwegian Coast Guard and the Swedish Coast Guard each used their own communication systems. While we didn't have the opportunity to directly exchange data with those systems, observing their system provided us with insights for benchmarking in GlobalCOP.

10.1.3. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

In UC4, the exercise took place within the maritime environment. The maritime environment, with its wide expanses of open water, brings unique challenges that aren't commonly faced in land-based settings. Waves, wind, and the significant distance between vessels or between a ship and its headquarters can introduce disturbances and weaken voice signals, making traditional voice communication less dependable. Furthermore, maritime operations often involve coordinating with multiple entities over large distances, where even a minor miscommunication can lead to major operational mistakes. Given the inherent challenges of the marine environment, conditions in UC4 naturally led to reduced voice communication.

For UC4, a Valkyries control post is set up to simulate the Command and Control (C2) functions (incident creation, resource allocation) and additionally the headquarter has the global vision of the scenario provided by GlobalCOP that runs the exercise in parallel in the Valkyrie environment.

Figure 9 - The various modes of communication through the Sigrun in UC4

Figure 9 shows the various modes of communication through the Sigrun system in UC4. Multiple sources of information and entities communicate through Sigrun. The arrows indicate the direction of communication between the sources, Sigrun, and the entities. The diagram highlights how Sigrun acts as a command centre, processing and facilitating the flow of information among various components in UC4.

10.1.4. CO.WP4.55: Use of wearables to support triage

For UC4, the use of wearables in the form of bracelets is tested for two purposes: as a system for identification, assigning a specific ID to each victim and labelling, making the assigned priority level visible for all FRs; and as a track and trace system for registering victims from ground zero before their handling by a qualified FR.

In this use case, two victims simulated having special conditions: one with an allergy to penicillin and another as a diabetic person. The wearables can be read by any smartphone with NFC enabled.

10.1.5. CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs

For UC4, a set with two first responders' teams (one near the victims and another close to the resources) is placed at a distance shorter than the maximum range of the UAV remote controller, around 100m. In this simulation, the first team attaches a small package to the UAV. The drone pilot of the first team then takes off the drone, flies to the second team, and lands the drone. Finally, the second team detaches the package and informs the pilot that the drone is ready to be returned.

The location where the FR Teams were situated had challenging access, with one team near the docks and another on the rocks closer to the sea, as depicted in the image below (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - Location of each First Responder Team

10.2. WP5 harmonization opportunities

In the case of VALKYRIES' UC4, the following opportunity resulting from the work of WP5 has been demonstrated: CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response: A enabler has been evaluated to the UC demonstrator to address this opportunity: CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters.

A detailed description of this opportunity is included in "D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation version A/1, Annex F".

The use of a standardised triage card by the different emergency services involved in assisting victims of MCI has been successfully tested and validated in preliminary tests and in use cases 1 to 3 of the VALKYRIES project. These tests included situations where first responders (FR) had to work with personal protective equipment (PPE) that could affect the usability of the solutions proposed by VALKYRIES (goggles, helmets, gloves, etc.).

Use Case 4 will specifically test the validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card, with the same characteristics as the previous use cases, but in an even more specific and demanding environment: rescue and assistance to victims in cold open water, where it is essential that the

FRs wear PPE that protects them from exposure to this threat, and where victims require specific approach due to hypothermia.

The evaluation of the proposed enabler in this very specific context does not necessarily compromise the validity already demonstrated in other disaster scenarios, but it can certainly provide very interesting information in order to establish the scope of its validity and to define recommendations for its use.

The assessment of this enabler in the UC4 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:

- Records made during the exercise: Collection (manually or automatically) of the information necessary to evaluate the MEs (mission success measures) and to determine whether or not the established KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were met. These records were made
- On-line questionnaires at the end of the UC4 to collect the evaluation of the participants in the UC simulation.

11. Validation and testing – Analysis of the results

The results of the tests carried out for each opportunity are detailed below. Both the preliminary tests and the tests performed at the time of the exercise are described. The detailed description of each test performed is described in the verification and validation document D7.3[3] and the methodology in D7.1 [4].

In this section, the summary of the results obtained is reported and the analysis of these data is performed.

11.1. WP4 Results

11.1.1. CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles

11.1.1.1. Preliminary Tests

The preliminary tests were designed and performed prior to the Project demonstrators (UCs) to evaluate and verify that VALKYRIES solution provides the location data of the vehicles and supports their updating position while simultaneously distribute it to the different users that require such info, via the GlobalCOP. The actual position of the personnel can be provided by an application on their mobile phones, as well as the vehicles equipped with AIS devices.

The functions were tested firstly in test environment (remotely with simulating tools) and after in small drills performed at SUMMA112 facility. In these tests and drills the location functions were successfully tested. Detailed information is provided in D7.5 Section 11.2.1.1 and in D7.7 11.1.1.1.

11.1.1.2. UC4 Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-15-T01- Location of Nearest Vessels	The system MUST be able to generate an updated vessels position picture that support the Operational Command to make better time dependent victims evacuation decisions	KPI 1: Information available	Yes (vessels position was received at the GLOBAL_COP) => Success
		KPI 2: Updated position of vessels	Updated vessels Position at SIGRUN: => Success
		KPI 3: time elapses	Time to display the information of vessels position: => Instantaneous

Table 5 – Results sheet CO.WP4-15-T01

The UC4 was conducted in a fjord where the 4G/5G signal is weak. As a result, there was sometimes delay in the GlobalCOP updates. However, this issue stemmed from the network, not the program itself. The challenges we faced were a result of weak 4G/5G signal strength in the fjord, which is an external factor related to network coverage. Such environmental conditions can adversely affect data transmission, leading to delays in updates or even complete loss of connectivity. This experience highlighted a broader concern: In situations where established

networks prove to be inconsistent or unreliable, what strategies or backup solutions can we implement to ensure uninterrupted operation and communication? It emphasizes the need to consider alternative solutions or contingency plans for areas with poor connectivity, ensuring that the program's effectiveness isn't compromised by external network issues.

11.1.2. CO.WP4.28. Cross Border Data Trace

During UC4 execution:

1. There was no registered breach of logical security of the Sigrun system.
2. The performance of the systems monitoring the developed module for Blockchain logging of data, reported no errors or discrepancies as per the expected results of the tests before UC execution.
3. Transactions and data/metadata exchanged through SIGRUN were logged smoothly with no loss of information or duplicates, causing no significant load to the systems employed, as expected.
by use of C2 tools

11.1.3. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

Results

11.1.3.1. Preliminary Tests

Several tests and verifications were performed prior to the UC4 and have been documented in D7.5 in Section 11.2.2, D7.6 in Section 11.2.2.1, and D7.7 in Section 11.1.3.1

11.1.3.2. UC4 Results

TEST	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-T03-Reduce Voice Communication	The test consists of verifying that the information update from SIGRUN is updated in real time in the Platform and the information is updated according to the central Database.	KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created by use of C2 tools and registered in SIGRUN Database)	Instantaneously
		KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created by use of C2 tools and registered in SIGRUN Database)	Instantaneously
		KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created by use of C2 tools and registered in SIGRUN Database)	Instantaneously

Table 6 – Results from testing CO-WP4-42-T03

As mentioned in the result of “CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles”, in UC4, the network conditions were unreliable, which made it challenging to conduct the GlobalCOP tests smoothly. However, the results for this opportunity from the previous UCs were satisfactory.

11.1.4. CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage

11.1.4.1. Preliminary Tests

To ensure the configuration and readability of the bracelets with any mobile device, tests were conducted the day before the simulation. During this test, each victim wore their respective bracelets to guarantee that proper readings were being made.

11.1.4.2. UC Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-55-T01- Use of wearable to support triage	The FR must be able to use a smartphone with NFC enabled to identify the special needs of the victim.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 99%	The FRs were able to read the information about the victims without <i>problems</i> .
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: 5000 ms	

Table 7 – Results from testing CO-WP4-55

11.1.5. CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs

11.1.5.1. Preliminary Tests

Performance tests were conducted before the test day. The week before the simulation, a logistics assistance test was performed, simulating a flight with a drone carrying a payload requested by a first responder after locating some victims. The purpose of these tests was to ensure that the drone would be able to fly in different weather conditions while carrying a payload.

11.1.5.2. UC Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-2-T01- Logistics assistance using UAVs	The test consists of verifying mission performance from the perspective of stakeholders, considering factors such as mission duration, incidents, and accessibility of the package by the second team.	KPI 1: Package received: YES/NO	YES
		KPI 2: Time of mission per distance between teams: $\leq x$ min/km	10 min/km
		KPI 3: Number of reported incidents in mission	0

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
		KPI 4: Stakeholders satisfaction: A subjective favourable perception by stakeholders	Greatly – 3 (11%) Considerably – 10 (36%) Moderate – 5 (18%) Limited – 2 (7%) Not at all – 0 (0%) N/A – 8 (29%)

Table 8 - Results from testing CO-WP4-2

The validation criteria are described below, where we have three possible results:

- A: Successful verification. Excellent results were observed (Package received YES, zero incidents, time of mission per distance between teams smaller than 5 min/km and stakeholder satisfaction over 80%)
- B: Successful verification. Outstanding results (Package received YES, maximum one incident, time of mission per distance between teams smaller than 10 min/m and stakeholder satisfaction over 50%).
- C: Failed verification. The minimum verification conditions have not been exceeded (Package received NO or time of mission per distance between teams greater than 10 min/m or stakeholder satisfaction under 50%).

According to the results presented on table 8, this opportunity had status **B**, successful verification with outstanding results.

11.2. WP5 Results

11.2.1. CO.WP5-7-2: TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in MCI and disasters.

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>VALKYRIES recommends adopting a standardized triage card, TASSICA 3, within the EU for documenting essential casualty details by various emergency services that might respond to an MCI.</p> <p>UC4 evaluated the effectiveness of the TASSICA 3 triage card in promoting interoperability among services (whether professional, volunteer, civilian, or military), ensuring fairness in treatment allocation, recording casualty data, and maintaining traceability during mass casualty and disaster events. The evaluation of this tool within the UC2 prototype was conducted using the subsequent verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effectiveness of this facilitator was objectively assessed in the course of UC4 through live data recording by VALKYRIES observers (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • A questionnaire was developed, after finishing the UC4 drill, among the participants to collect their opinion on the impact of using TASSICA 3 triage card integrated in their operating procedures (VERIFICATION ACTION #2).
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80%	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.		by stakeholders.	
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

triage card, as perceived by first responders.			
Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (GREATLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Horten (Norway), 27 September 2023	
	Participants	RS Eyvind Eckbo (Norwegian rescue society) first responders involved in UC4 drill.	
	Description	The validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card was assessed on the basis of the data recorded by VALKYRIES' evaluators during the conduct of the UC4 cross-border MCI drill. A data sheet was defined to manually record the information needed to evaluate TASSICA 3 triage card during the UC execution.	

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

	Execution	<p>This evaluation exercise was carried out in a harmonised manner with the other VALKYRIES enablers.</p> <p>UC4 simulated a cross-border maritime accident involving two vessels carrying a number of passengers, requiring search and rescue, victim care, as well as the clean-up of oil or chemical spills in the sea drifting towards the shore. Resources from several countries will be involved in the incident: Norway, Sweden and Denmark.</p> <p>A number of first responders have integrated TASSICA 3 cards into their triage operating procedures. These first responders received specific online training on the day of the simulation, prior to the drill.</p> <p>Collection of the information necessary to evaluate this enabler was made manually by a network of VALKYRIES' evaluators. The number and location of those evaluators during the execution of the UC was defined in order to properly carry out the data collection for the evaluation of the proposed enabler.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage threshold (TASSICA 3): 53 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate (TASSICA 3): 100% (ACHIEVED)
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	See section 11.3: Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation, 11.3.1 Offline Survey.
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Horten (Norway), 27 September 2023.
	Participants	First responders involved in UC4 drill.
	Description	<p>A questionnaire was used to collect feedback from participants on each facets of the UC: "Questionnaire for feedback survey with participants in the joint Norway-Sweden-Denmark cross-border exercise in response to MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)". Some of the questions (42 to 49) were adressed to first responders using TASSICA 3 cards, related to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which the card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on life-saving gestures, ensure

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

		<p>traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. • Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. • Rating on enabling best execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other procedures. • Overall level of satisfaction
	Execution	<p>At the end of UC4, members of the emergency services participating in the exercise who used the TASSICA 3 card were asked to complete a survey. The respondents answered the survey anonymously. The personal details of the victims used during the simulation exercise are fictitious.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 33% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 66,67% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: 66,67% (NOT ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-rater reliability: GREATLY AGREED • Decision-making confidence: GREATLY AGREED • Traceability: CONSIDERABLY AGREED • Victim information completeness and accuracy: CONSIDERABLY AGREED • First responder wellbeing: NONE (MEDIAN: MODERATE) • Task execution efficiency: CONSIDERABLY AGREED • Collaboration efficiency: GREATLY AGREED • Stakeholder satisfaction: NONE (MEDIAN: CONSIDERABLY)
	History of corrective measures	

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

Lessons learned	
Quality	C: High adequacy (60-79% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	See section 11.3: Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation, 11.3.1 Offline Survey.
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 9 - Results from testing CO-WP5-7-2

11.2.2. WP5 UC4 demonstration: evidence of implementation and compliance:

Evidence 1: Victims' datasheet

ID PAX	BENCHMARK 1T PRIORITY PAX	ID SIGRUN	INCIDENT	PRIORITY 1T SIGRUN	ID TASSICA 3	PRIORITY TASSICA 3	ACCUR TASSICA 3	START 1T TASSICA 3	END 1T TASSICA 3	TIME 1T TASSICA 3
3	1	victim_3	Collision leisure craft <-> Container - Oslofjorden	1	A230225	1	1	12:19:15	12:20:00	0:00:45
4	2	victim_4	Collision leisure craft <-> Container - Oslofjorden	2	A230228	2	1	12:14:15	12:15:00	0:00:45
2	3	victim_2	Collision leisure craft <-> Container - Oslofjorden	3	A230226	3	1	12:15:00	12:16:00	0:01:00
1	3	victim_1	Collision leisure craft <-> Container - Oslofjorden	3	A230227	3	1	12:16:15	12:17:15	0:01:00
							100,00%			
								0:00:53		

Figure 11 – WP5 Victims' datasheet

Evidence 2: Related survey results (Questionnaire for feedback survey with participants in the joint Norway-Sweden-Denmark cross-border exercise in response to MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents), questions 42 to 49).

QUESTIONS	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49
Greatly	2	2	1	1	0	1	2	1
Considerably	1	1	2	2	1	2	0	1
Moderate	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
Limited	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Not at all	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
N/A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
N KPI compliance	3	3	3	3	1	3	2	2
% KPI compliance	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	33,33%	100,00%	66,67%	66,67%
PREDOMINANT RESPONSE	GREATLY	GREATLY	CONSIDERABLY	CONSIDERABLY	NONE (MEDIAN: MODERATE)	CONSIDERABLY	GREATLY	NONE (MEDIAN: CONSIDERABLY)

Figure 12 – WP5 Survey results

11.3. Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation

The evaluation of the UC4 involved a comprehensive approach aimed at gathering feedback and insights from the participants. Two phases of evaluation (offline and online survey) were conducted to ensure a thorough understanding of the participants' experiences and perceptions.

In the initial phase, participants were provided with an offline survey after UC4. This survey was structured to cover various aspects of the UC4, encompassing tools and technologies, organization, and overall satisfaction. This structured approach allowed for a systematic assessment of participant responses.

A follow-up online survey was conducted to explore further participants' experiences, perspectives, and suggestions regarding the UC4. This online survey aimed to provide a more comprehensive assessment of participant satisfaction and to pinpoint specific areas for improvement. The questionnaire can be found in Annex C.

11.3.1. Offline Survey

Survey for Exercise itself

The survey questions were consistent with those used in previous UC1, UC2, and UC3 evaluations. This consistency facilitated comparative analysis and ensured that participants could provide feedback in a familiar format, enhancing the reliability and validity of the evaluation.

Questions Q1-Q14 are for the evaluation of the exercise itself.

Participant backgrounds brought significant depth to the exercise, with a majority (68%) having prior experience in similar exercises.

In terms of execution, the choice of a full-scale exercise was seen as appropriate and effective in demonstrating proposed solutions. However, while there was satisfaction with the preparatory aspects, some logistical components and timeline management did not fully meet participant expectations, suggesting areas for further refinement. Incidents like transportation delays and the need for better location coordination emerged as opportunities for enhancing logistical robustness in future exercises. Regarding the incident at the end of the exercise (grounded observer boat), it serves as a valuable example of the unpredictable situations that can emerge during such exercises. Responding to these unexpected incidents is invaluable, especially from the standpoint of emergency preparedness.

Regarding training, the exercise provided valuable insights into innovative solutions and methodologies, although responses suggested variability in the training's comprehensiveness. This unevenness in participant experience with the training components of the exercise points to a need for a more uniform approach to educational aspects in future exercise.

Communication emerged as a two-sided issue in the feedback, being credited for effective information exchange and situational awareness but also pinpointed as needing consistency and reliability enhancements. The feedback called for clearer exercise objectives, improved logistical coordination, and refined observational and information-sharing protocols.

While the exercise met its primary objectives—simulating a realistic emergency scenario, identifying operational gaps, and introducing innovative solutions—participant feedback highlighted several areas for improvement. These insights are invaluable for the planning and execution of future exercises, indicating a necessity for enhanced logistics, consistent communication strategies, and comprehensive training approaches. Addressing these areas could improve participant satisfaction and the overall impact of such emergency response exercises in preparing for real-world scenarios. For more details, please refer to Annex D1.

Survey for Selected Valkyries solutions

During UC4, several tools were tested, including the following:

- GlobalCOP
- Tassica 3 Triage Card
- Aratos Tap2SOS bracelets
- Drone/BodyCam

Questions Q22-Q69 are for the evaluation of the Valkyries solutions.

Due to the limited number of respondents for the Valkyries solution questionnaire, the analysis primarily focuses on providing qualitative insights. While calculating percentages or statistical significance may not be meaningful with such a small sample size, we have aimed to identify valuable suggestions for improvement and any unique insights shared by the participants. Additionally, it's important to note that a follow-up survey was conducted to gather more comprehensive feedback and address the limitations of the initial response rate.

Conversation log

The following analysis refers to the conversation log among 9 participants (It also included conversations about topics other than Valkyries tools).

- **Communication Challenges:** Participants discussed the challenges they faced with communication, particularly with different technologies. There was mention of difficulties using 'WhatsApp' as a communication tool due to delays and the stress caused by its inefficiency for UC4. There was also a mention of issues with radio functionality, which hindered the effective deployment of drones for logistical support.
- **Use of Drones:** Two drone pilots talk about the difficulties they encountered, especially regarding the drone not recognizing victims due to their clothing. They also talked about the usefulness of drones in transporting small items quickly, and problems with the live stream and communication links. They also discussed the potential usefulness of a flashlight on drones for visibility and the importance of victims recognizing drones as part of the rescue effort. The discussion on drone operations provides insights into the practical challenges and opportunities associated with using drones in maritime emergency scenarios.
- **Triage system:** There was discussion about the triage process, particularly regarding the use of triage cards and the categorization of victims. The participants seemed to appreciate the color-coding system but suggested immediate categorization would have been more efficient. They also discussed the challenges with the form, such as its size, readability, and language used, suggesting it needed simplification for practical use by all responders, not just medical professionals.

- **Training and preparedness:** Participants emphasized the importance of training and preparedness during emergency response, noting that increased familiarity with the system and additional training could improve performance. This feedback highlights the need for more comprehensive training opportunities and enhancing participants' proficiency with the tools and procedures utilized.
- **Technology and Equipment Issues:** Participants brought up several issues related to the technology used, including problems with electronic devices like a bodycam that kept disconnecting and issues with 4G connectivity at sea. The need for reliable, robust, and user-friendly technology was a key subject.

The conversation log among participants reveals key challenges and opportunities in UC4 related to communication, drone operations, the triage system, training, and technology issues, emphasizing the importance of addressing these aspects for more effective emergency responses in maritime scenarios.

Tap2SOS

The feedback on the Tap2SOS provides valuable insights into its usability and practicality in emergency response scenarios.

- **Necessity of a scanner/android phone for first responders**
This indicates that first responders require access to specific technology to interpret the data on the bracelets. Although digital records are efficient and capable of storing more detailed information than physical tags, their utility is limited if first responders lack immediate, uninterrupted access to the requisite technology or are not proficient in using these devices.
- **Time consumption for data access**
In a triage situation, speed is of the essence as first responders assess the severity of injuries to prioritize care. A system that requires multiple steps just to access vital information could cause crucial delays. This feedback suggests the need for a more efficient interface or system — perhaps one that allows instant access to data upon scanning, without needing multiple steps for app activation and data retrieval.
- **Non-waterproof nature of the reading device**
Emergencies can occur in any environment, including those involving water. The lack of waterproofing on the reading devices can severely limit their usability in such situations. It's imperative for emergency equipment to be durable and versatile enough to withstand various environmental conditions.
- **Difficulty in operating the phone with neoprene gloves**
The practicality of equipment in crisis scenarios is crucial. First responders should be able to operate devices seamlessly while wearing protective gear. If the device's interface isn't compatible with the gloves responders are likely to wear, especially in cold or hazardous conditions, it could impede the triage process, potentially risking lives.
- **Issues with using the phone in cold climates**
The operational challenges posed by cold climates — such as battery drainage or difficulty in handling the device with gloves. For a triage system to be reliable, it must perform consistently across different scenarios, including various weather conditions.

These insights can guide improvements to enhance the Tap2SOS's efficiency, durability, and adaptability, ultimately contributing to more effective triage processes in various conditions.

11.3.2. Follow-up Online Survey

After the initial offline survey, an additional online survey was conducted to further investigate participants' experiences, perspectives, and suggestions regarding the UC4. This survey featured five open-ended questions, designed to encourage participants to give more detailed and qualitative feedback.

Participants appreciated the realistic approach of UC4, emphasizing its non-simulated nature, which allowed for the discovery of real-world issues. They also found value in the opportunity to experiment with innovative solutions for challenging emergency situations at sea. The successful drone-aided rescue of a civilian at sea and the visualization of incidents on the GlobalCOP platform were highlighted as effective aspects.

Challenges and issues were also raised, including the need for more cross-border communication and coordination. Some participants noted the requirement for tablets or smartphones for first responders and reported technical challenges with live streams from body cameras and drones. The complexity of implementing new technologies and proposed solutions was recognized as both a challenge and an opportunity for improvement.

The mixed feedback on technological tools and Valkyries solutions included issues with drone and body cam functionality, connectivity problems with Tab2SOS bracelets, and the need for more detailed tool descriptions. However, GlobalCOP received positive feedback as a valuable solution for first responders.

Participants also suggested dividing observers into different groups for improved visibility, emphasizing the importance of emergency preparedness and technology use, and recommending clearer collaboration and harmonization across countries.

In conclusion, the feedback from participants emphasizes the need for ongoing improvement and optimization of tools and technologies, improved cross-border communication, and more thorough training to enhance the effectiveness of future emergency response exercises in maritime environments. The strengths of UC4, such as its realistic approach and innovative solutions, should be further leveraged, while addressing identified areas for improvement. For more details, please refer to Annex D2.

12. Conclusions (Summary of the debriefing, recommendations and lessons learned)

Before proceeding to the conclusions, it's essential to revisit the key operational elements observed during UC4.

In UC4, a command centre was established on the Norwegian Coast Guard ship, utilizing the GLOBAL COP application for a unified operational perspective. There were two Field Operational Centres (FOC): on the observer's boat and on the Swedish Coast Guard ship, both with GlobalCOP available to get a global or/and local operational picture. In addition, the FOC on the observer's boat used command-and-control tools for mission creation and manual resource allocation for the incident. Victims' personal and medical details, including triage information, were managed from this FOC.

On-site, various tools were employed: SIGRUN, GLOBAL COP, Aratos Tap2SOS bracelets for victims' data, TASSICA 3 Triage Cards for manual triage, and Particle's Staff Tracking app for real-time staff updates. A background-running Blockchain encryption module, a body camera, and a drone were also used, the latter providing video to GLOBAL COP and featuring autonomous victim detection in the sea. Moreover, live ship positions were automatically updated in GLOBAL COP using AIS signals and a Python script transferring the signals to SIGRUN.

A survey was conducted to receive feedback on these tools from participants. Because the observer boat was grounded on its way back to shore, schedules were somewhat delayed. As holding a debriefing at sea or on the shore was challenging, the debriefings were conducted online on 5th October.

The evaluation of UC4 was a comprehensive effort that included both offline and online surveys to gather feedback and insights from participants. This approach aimed to ensure a thorough understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions regarding various aspects of the exercise, as well as the tools and technologies used.

In the offline survey phase, participants provided feedback on the exercise itself, emphasizing the suitability of a full-scale exercise to demonstrate proposed solutions. While there was overall satisfaction with the preparatory aspects, some logistical components and timeline management fell short of expectations, indicating areas for refinement. Unexpected incidents, such as the grounding of the observer boat, illustrated the unpredictability of real-world scenarios and the importance of effective response.

Training emerged as a variable factor in participants' experiences, suggesting the need for a more uniform approach to educational aspects in future exercises. Communication was both credited for effective information exchange and situational awareness and identified as needing enhancements in consistency and reliability.

The survey for selected Valkyries solutions provided qualitative insights due to a limited number of respondents. While statistical analysis may not be meaningful with this sample size, valuable suggestions for improvement and unique insights were identified. The conversation log among participants further clarified key challenges and opportunities related to communication, drone operations, the triage system, training, and technology issues.

Feedback specific to the Tap2SOS system emphasized the necessity of scanners or Android phones for first responders and concerns regarding time consumption for data access, waterproofing, and compatibility with gloves. These insights point toward opportunities to enhance the system's efficiency, durability, and adaptability.

The follow-up online survey generated feedback emphasizing the realism of UC4, participants' appreciation for the non-simulated approach, and the value of experimenting with innovative solutions. Challenges included the need for improved cross-border communication, the requirement for tablets or smartphones for first responders, and technical issues with live streams and connectivity. The complexity of implementing new technologies was both a challenge and an opportunity for improvement.

In conclusion, the feedback from participants emphasizes the continuous need for improvement and optimization of tools and technologies, enhanced cross-border communication, and more comprehensive training to maximize the effectiveness of future emergency response exercises in maritime environments. UC4's strengths, such as its realistic approach and innovative solutions, should be leveraged while addressing identified areas for improvement. These insights are valuable for the ongoing development of emergency response capabilities and the successful implementation of innovative solutions.

13. References and bibliography

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2. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D2.7 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases”
3. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D2.8 Architecture Design Document”
4. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.1 Test Bed and Evaluation Methodology”
5. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation”
6. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.4 Reference Integration and Lesson Learned Report”
7. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.5 Report on the use case Spain-Portugal”
8. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.6 Report on the use case Slovakia-Italy”
9. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable “D7.7 Report on the use case Bulgaria-Greece”

14. Annex A - Glossary

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
C2	Command and Control (post)
COP	Common Operational Picture
DoA	Description of Action (project)
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
EX	Exercise
EXCon	Exercise Control
EXSPEC	EXSPEC – Exercise Specification (also Demonstration Specification)
FER	Final Evaluation Report
FIR	First Impression Report
FOC	Field Operational Centre
FR	First Responder
FX	Field Exercise
JRCC	Joint Rescue Coordination Center
GP	GLOBAL COP (one of the tools)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIVEX	Live Exercise (also FX - Field Exercise)
MCI	Multi-Casualty Incident
RS	Redningselskapet, (Norwegian Society for Sea Rescue)
SAHS	FRS Ambulance
SAR	Search and Rescue
STA	Secondary Training Audience
TA	Training audience
TApp	Application for Digitalizing Triage Process
TC	Test Conditions
TOs	Training Objectives
TP	Technical Partner
TPC	Technical partners coordinator
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTX	Table Top Exercise (also CPX – Command Post Exercise)
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
VOST	Virtual Operations Support Team

Table 10 - Glossary

15. Annex B – UC4 implementation plan

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

for execution of exercise related to the VALKYRIES UC#4

GENERAL DATA

The VALKYRIES project aims to assess the current protocols, technologies, and procedures used by European first responders and propose pre-standardization and harmonization measures. These actions are designed to enhance collaboration among first responders during cross-border incidents. The project consortium recommends various initiatives to improve the effectiveness of first responders in Multi-Casualty Cross-border incidents, implementing these proposals in the SIGRUN integration platform. The effectiveness of these proposals was demonstrated in UC4.

Goal of this document is to summarize and prepare all the information related to demonstrations of stated UCs and necessary to implement them in effective manner with aim to present VALKYRIES elements on a relatively simple case before moving on to an extensive deployment.

The data summarized in this document will also serve for other purposes and needs of the project.

FULL NAME:	CROSS-BORDER RESPONSE TO THE DISASTER CONTAINING THE SPREADING OF TOXIC SUBSTANCES Section of pollution on sea in international waters (Norway-Sweden-Denmark)
NICKNAME:	UC4
SERIAL NUMBER:	004
LEVEL:	OPERATIONAL
FORM:	LIVEX
TYPE:	FX with the elements of TTX
DATES:	26 – 27 September 2023
AREA:	Bolærne (South-east of Tønsberg and Horten), Norway
OFFICER SCHEDULING AND CONDUCTING THE EXERCISE	Leif Inge Magnussen, University of South-Eastern Norway (USN)
EXERCISE DIRECTOR:	Jon Herman Ulvensøen, USN
PLANNING OFFICER:	Fabio Augusto de Alcantara Andrade and Leif Inge Magnussen
LOGISTIC OFFICER:	Jon Herman Ulvensøen

EVALUATION DIRECTOR:	Meritxell Bassols Tayeda	
HOST INSTITUTION:	USN with support of Norwegian Coastal Administration	
PARTICIPANTS:	Norwegian Coast Guard Swedish Coast Guard Norwegian Society for Sea Rescue (Redningselskapet, RS) Norwegian Coastal Administration Interkommunalt utvalg mot forurensing (IUA)	INDRA ISEMI AREU SUMA112 HRT USN

Table 11 – Annex B: UC4 general data

Nordic Exercise

The Nordic exercise was run by the Norwegian Coastal administration, and the UC4 was part of an annual joint exercise between Norway, Denmark, and Sweden.

The Norwegian Coastal Administration, responsible for national pollution preparedness, coordinated and trained various emergency resources from the private, municipal, and state sectors. Approximately 200 individuals participated in the Nordic exercise, focusing on interaction, planning, and operations related to acute pollution incidents. The director of emergency preparedness emphasized the importance of practice and cooperation among neighbouring countries, ensuring readiness for potential accidents that may require cross-border assistance. The exercise covered various aspects, including coordination among different stakeholders, action planning based on available information, setting priorities, and practical training in pollution response techniques.

Actor

- Demonstration coordinator: University of South-Eastern Norway-USN
- Overall exercise coordinator: Norwegian Coastal Administration and Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection (Direktoratet for Samfunnssikkerhet og Beredskap, DSB)
- Key stakeholders of first responders: Norwegian Coast guard and Norwegian Coastal Administration
- Norwegian Coastal Administration

Participants in Nordic Exercise

- Norwegian Coastal Administration
- Norwegian Society for Sea Rescue
- Swedish Coast Guard
- Danish Coast Guard
- IUA Vestfold
- IUA Østfold

Vessels of Units

The coastal administration organizes vessels included coast guard from Norway, Sweden and Denmark and oil collecting units.

Figure 13 – Annex B: Norwegian Coast Guard – KV Nornen

Figure 14 – Annex B: Kystverkets Fartøy – OV Ryvingen

Figure 15 – Annex B: Danish Coast Guard

Figure 16 – Annex B: Swedish Coast Guard

Figure 17 – Annex B: Flybåten for observers

Figure 18 – Annex B: Redningselskapet

On-Board Activities and Coordination: Norwegian Coast Guard

The Norwegian coast guard participated in the oil spill Øvelse Nordisk (Exercise Nordic) with their vessel, KV Nornen. KV Nornen assumed the role of the on-scene commander for the duration of the exercise. On board KV Nornen, personnel from the coastal administration were also present. The team from the coastal administration consisted of an exercise leader and a deputy responsible for managing the exercise and allocating resources as needed. The coastal

administration personnel received assistance from the coast guard in handling internal communication on board KV Nornen. Additionally, the coast guard personnel were responsible for updating the log and various software systems during the exercise.

Communication with other ships was carried out using radios, both VHF and UHF, and the language of communication was Norwegian and Swedish. Internal communication within KV Nornen also relied on radios. The coastal administration personnel communicated with the onshore command center using phones and email.

KV Nornen launched its drone multiple times during the exercise. The drone's primary purpose was to inspect the oil spill containment booms and the simulated oil spill. The live video feed from the drone was streamed through Microsoft Teams. This allowed personnel on shore to observe the video feed in real-time and communicate requests using the chat function. During one of the drone operations, a fault was discovered with one of the oil spill containment booms. Information regarding this fault was reported to the ship responsible for operating the boom through radio communication.

Figure 19 – Annex B: Live stream of drone video using Teams

To establish a collective situational awareness, various software applications were employed, including:

1. Barentswatch: www.barentswatch.no/en
2. Kystinfo: <https://a3.kystverket.no/kystinfo>
3. Internal coast guard software

Most of the information available in both Barentswatch and Kystinfo is accessible to the public. These platforms provide a wealth of information pertinent to maritime traffic. Within these software solutions, users can select different maps and access weather and sea state data. Furthermore, users can track the real-time positions of all vessels within the Norwegian economic zone, encompassing the northern regions of Denmark and the western coast of Sweden.

Barentswatch offers a unique feature known as the "incident room." This feature is not accessible to the public; only assets directly involved in an incident can access the information contained therein. The "incident room" includes a brief description of the incident and details about all assets, including ships and personnel, engaged in the incident. During the exercise, the coast guard and the coastal administration experimented with the capability to share videos and images using Barentswatch and Kystinfo. The test yielded positive results; however, it is currently not possible to share live video streams through these platforms.

Figure 20 – Annex B: "Incident room" in Barentswatch

On-Board Activities and Coordination: Swedish Coast Guard

The Swedish Coast Guard was primarily focused on enhancing their capabilities in responding to oil spills. Their activities were centered around the deployment and testing of oil spill sweep systems. The Swedish Coast Guard tested a single vessel sweep system (Figure 21), an advanced method for oil recovery. This system is particularly effective in scenarios where resources are

limited or when spills occur in harder-to-reach locations. In addition to testing equipment, there was an emphasis on oil spill response training. This involved simulated exercises that required the crew to strategize, deploy, and operate the oil recovery equipment (Figure 22).

Figure 21 – Annex B: Single vessel sweep system

Figure 22 – Annex B: Deployment of oil spill sweep system

The Swedish Coast Guard utilized a program with functionalities similar to GlobalCOP, a software known for providing real-time information and enabling effective communication among various stakeholders during crisis situations. By integrating features tailored for marine use, GlobalCOP could improve its operational effectiveness during maritime crises.

Operation of Drone and Bodycam

The drone performed two missions: autonomous flight, looking for possible victims, with its position being updated in real-time on GlobalCOP and streaming images; and the logistic mission, sending a package to the FR team.

Regarding the first mission, the drone performed a flight in an area covered by water and the beach, as shown in the image below.

Figure 23 – Annex B: Area covered by the drone

This mission didn't yield the expected results due to the suits worn by the actors; the system was not able to identify them as humans. However, in the tests before the simulation, we could identify them in their normal clothes, as seen in the image below.

Figure 24 – Annex B: Streaming from the drone camera

Regarding the logistic mission, it performed according to expectations, with the package being delivered quickly and without any reported issues.

The bodycam was attached to one of the FRs in the RS vessel, and it was streamed to a link accessible through GlobalCOP. The streaming was available until the moment when the FR left the vessel, and some connection issues between the router and the camera started to occur.

GlobalCOP

GlobalCOP (see Figure 25) was deployed at both the Headquarters and at the Field Operational Center in the rescue society's SAR boat, but were not much used due to its rather simple functionality compared to the systems already in use especially made for sea operations. At the same time, its simpleness and responsiveness can be a strength when used in stressed and demanding situations. Technically, GlobalCOP performed very well without any errors or latency, and was highly reliable.

Figure 25- Annex B: GlobalCOP overview

Also, GlobalCOP was appreciated by the Field Operational Center because it unlike the other systems also provides a live view of the victims' triage status as shown in Figure 26. A more detailed list of the victims' medical condition and history was also available in GlobalCOP.

Figure 26 – Annex B: Overview of victims

16. Annex C - FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRES

16.1. Annex C1 Offline Survey

Questionnaire for feedback survey with participants in the joint Norway-Sweden-Denmark cross-border exercise in response to MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)

Dear Participant,

Thank you for taking part in the joint Norway-Sweden-Denmark exercise conducted as part of the VALKYRIES European project. This initiative aims to develop and validate innovative technological solutions, operational procedures, education, training, and collaboration methods for handling multi-casualty incidents (MCIs).

We greatly appreciate your feedback on the exercise itself, as well as on the technological tools, operational procedures, and training materials presented.

Your expert opinion is essential in advancing the pre-standardization efforts for VALKYRIES project solutions at the EU level.

Please be assured that all answers provided will remain anonymous.

Thank you for your cooperation!

General Information

- Type of organization:
- Role in organization:
- Years of experience:

Questionnaire Structure and Focus

This questionnaire consists of two parts:

- Exercise Evaluation:** Questions **for all participants** (Questions 1-21, which will take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete)
- Valkyries Solution Evaluation:** **Mainly for first responder feedback**, but all are welcome to contribute. (Questions 22-69)
 - Questions for GlobalCOP (Questions 22-41, which will take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete)
 - Questions for Triage Card (Questions 42-49, which will take approximately 4-5 minutes to complete)
 - Questions for Tap2SOS bracelet (Questions 50-69, which will take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete)

A. Exercise Evaluation Questionnaire

Questions 1-21 are applicable to all participants and will take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete. If a question does not apply to you, please select the option N/A.

- Have you participated in or observed emergency response exercises or simulations in the past?
 - Yes
 - No

- How important is it to compare different emergency response scenarios and create common plans for conducting and reporting demonstrations

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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- According to your opinion, was the selection of a full-scale type of exercise adequate for the demonstration of the proposed solutions?
 - Yes
 - No

Please, elaborate.

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- Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics)

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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Please, elaborate.

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- Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed solutions in the exercise.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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Please, elaborate.

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- To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real-life emergency?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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7. To what extent did the selected scenario showcase operational gaps in the response to a Multi-Casualty Incident and the added value that the proposed solutions bring in order to cover these gaps?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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8. The extent, to which the objectives of the exercise i.e., effective exchange of information between different first responders and increased situational awareness for the agencies engaged in a MCI, are achieved.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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9. How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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10. How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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11. The extent, to which the timeline of the exercise was appropriately managed and followed the pre-defined schedule.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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12. Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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13. Your participation in the exercise, the implementation of tools and interaction with other stakeholders allowed you to increase your knowledge on innovative solutions and newly proposed methodologies that can be of added value for your operational work.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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14. Please, indicate strengths and also areas that require improvement, to be considered for future exercises.

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15. Regarding Location Tracking, to what extent did harmonization efforts successfully improve the tracking of vehicles locations during exercise?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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16. Regarding cross border data trace, to what extent did the exercise improve information sharing and data traceability among responding organizations?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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17. Regarding digitalization Impact on Voice Communication, how much did the digitalization actions reduce the need for voice communication by transferring information digitally?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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18. Regarding use of wearable to support triage, did the use of the wearable bracelet with specific medical data facilitate triage and reduce risks for the victims

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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19. Regarding utilizing data from the Harmonization tasks for Learning, how valuable is the data from harmonization tasks for learning and improving future emergency response actions

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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20. Regarding logistics assistance using UAVs, how much did the use of drones expedite equipment transportation between first responder teams?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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21. Regarding training for Valkyries solution (if you haven't received training, please skip questions 21.1 -21.4)

21.1 To what extent the training with the presented joint multinational training Kit for first responders will be helpful for the completion of your tasks in Multi casualty incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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21.2 To what extent the training with the proposed **joint multinational training kit** for first responders enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border multi casualty incidents compared to the existing training courses?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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21.3 How likely is to recommend to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed **joint multinational training kit** for first responders in multi casualty incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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21.4 Overall, are you satisfied with the proposed **joint multinational training kit** for first responders in multi casualty incidents in terms of content?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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If you did not use the Valkyries Solution, the survey ends here.

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Your feedback is invaluable to us and will help enhance our future initiatives.

For the rest, please continue answering the remaining questions.

B. Valkyries Solution Section

This section of the questionnaire (questions 22 to 69) is for participants who used “Valkyries Solution” during the exercise, and is structured as follows:

- Questions for GlobalCOP (questions 22-41, it’ll take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete)
- Questions for Triage Card (questions 42-49, it’ll take approximately 4-5 minutes to complete)

- Questions for Tap2SOS bracelet (questions 50-69, it'll take approximately 7-10 minutes to complete)

Please select which of the VALKYRIES solutions you have been using during the exercise (Multiple answers are possible)

- PARTICLE: GLOBAL COP
- TASSICA: Triage Card
- ARATOS and BlockChain2050: Tap2SOS bracelet

This section of the questionnaire (questions 22 to 41) is for participants who used "GlobalCOP" during the exercise. If you did not use it, proceed to questions 42.

If a question does not apply to you, please select the option N/A.

Effectiveness

22. The proposed solution performed as expected according to the functions it was designed to.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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23. To what extent the solution assisted the completion of your tasks.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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24. To what extent the proposed solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents).

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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Efficiency

25. The proposed solution enables the faster implementation of your tasks in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents).

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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26. The proposed solution enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents) compared to the existing tools and conditions.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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Satisfaction

27. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed solution
Please, elaborate.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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28. To what extent the proposed solution is easy to be used by a first responder

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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29. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed solution.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
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30. To what extent does the operation of the proposed solution requires significant scientific and/or technical competence by the first responder.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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31. The proposed solution can easily interoperate with other systems and/or procedures used/ followed by your organization for the response to an MCI.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
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32. To what extent would you suggest to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed solution?

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1	N/A
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33. The proposed solution is expected to significantly enhance the collaboration of the first responder during his/her operational duties.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
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34. Are the victims' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Highly Secured 5	Secured 4	Average 3	Marginally Secured 2	Not Secured 1	N/A
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35. Are the first responders' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Highly Secured 5	Secured 4	Average 3	Marginally Secured 2	Not Secured 1	N/A
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36. Do you think that integrating the solution into standardization or regulatory frameworks at the organizational and/or national level will be necessary

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1	N/A
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37. Does the proposed solution bring added value to the management of and response to cross-border MCIs?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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38. To what extent do you think the proposed solution demonstrated effective basic operation during the exercise at sea, despite challenging conditions

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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39. Overall, were you satisfied with the functionalities and the use of the proposed solution?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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40. Please, indicate key success factors of the implementation of the proposed solution.

41. Please add recommendations for improvement for the proposed solution.

This section of the questionnaire (questions 42 to 49) is for participants who used “TASSICA Triage Card” during the exercise. If you did not use it, proceed to questions 50.

If a question does not apply to you, please select the option N/A.

42. To what extent do you think that the TASSICA 3 card helps to homogenise the triage priorities assigned to victims in an MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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43. To what extent do you think that the TASSICA 3 card helps you to decide which life-saving gestures are appropriate for a given victim in a MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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44. To what extent do you think the TASSICA 3 triage card helps to ensure the traceability of a victim at the scene of an MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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45. To what extent do you think the TASSICA 3 triage card facilitates the recording of victims' health information in the response to a MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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46. To what extent do you think that the TASSICA 3 card reduces the stress of healthcare personnel in decision-making in the triage of victims in a MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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47. Do you think that the use of the same standardised triage card throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents)?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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48. To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card allows you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a MCI compared to other cards?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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49. How satisfied are you overall with the TASSICA 3 triage card you have used?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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This section of the questionnaire (questions 50 to 69) is for participants who used “Tap2SOS bracelet” during the exercise. If you did not use it, proceed to the end of the questionnaire.

If a question does not apply to you, please select the option N/A.

Effectiveness

50. The proposed solution performed as expected according to the functions it was designed to.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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51. To what extent the solution assisted the completion of your tasks.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

52. To what extent the proposed solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents).

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

Efficiency

53. The proposed solution enables the faster implementation of your tasks in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents).

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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54. The proposed solution enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a cross-border MCI (Multi Casualty Incidents) compared to the existing tools and conditions.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

Satisfaction

55. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed solution
Please, elaborate.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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56. To what extent the proposed solution is easy to be used by a first responder

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
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57. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed solution.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
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58. To what extent does the operation of the proposed solution requires significant scientific and/or technical competence by the first responder.

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

59. The proposed solution can easily interoperate with other systems and/or procedures used/followed by your organization for the response to an MCI.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
---------------------	------------	----------------------------------	---------------	------------------------	-----

60. To what extent would you suggest to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed solution?

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1	N/A
-----------------------	-------------	--------------	---------------	-------------------------	-----

61. The proposed solution is expected to significantly enhance the collaboration of the first responder during his/her operational duties.

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree /nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1	N/A
---------------------	------------	----------------------------------	---------------	------------------------	-----

62. Are the victims' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Highly Secured 5	Secured 4	Average 3	Marginally Secured 2	Not Secured 1	N/A
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63. Are the first responders' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Highly Secured 5	Secured 4	Average 3	Marginally Secured 2	Not Secured 1	N/A
---------------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------------	------------------	-----

64. Do you think that integrating the solution into standardization or regulatory frameworks at the organizational and/or national level will be necessary

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1	N/A
-----------------------	-------------	--------------	---------------	-------------------------	-----

65. Does the proposed solution bring added value to the management of and response to cross-border MCIs?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

66. To what extent do you think the proposed solution demonstrated effective basic operation during the exercise at sea, despite challenging conditions

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

67. Overall, were you satisfied with the functionalities and the use of the proposed solution?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1	N/A
--------------	-------------------	---------------	--------------	-----------------	-----

68. Please, indicate key success factors of the implementation of the proposed solution.

69. Please add recommendations for improvement for the proposed solution.

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Your feedback is invaluable to us and will help enhance our future initiatives.

16.2. Annex C2 Follow-up online Survey

Questionnaire for feedback survey UC4

This survey is designed to explore further your perspectives and experiences during the UC4. While the initial survey provided valuable feedback, this follow-up survey aims to capture even more detailed and specific feedback.

Unlike the initial survey, this follow-up survey contains five subjective questions, allowing you to share your thoughts, observations, and suggestions in greater detail.

As with the initial survey, please be assured that all responses will be treated with confidentiality.

1. What aspects of UC4 did you find most effective or successful?

Enter your answer

2. Were there any specific challenges or issues you encountered during UC4?

Enter your answer

3. How would you rate the effectiveness of communication and collaboration among participants and teams during UC4?

Enter your answer

4. Did the technological tools (drone, body cam) and Valkyries solutions (GlobalCOP, TASSICA Triage Card, Tab2SOS) used in UC4 meet your expectations? If not, please specify areas for improvement.

Enter your answer

5. Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience in UC4?

Enter your answer

17. Annex D – Results from the analysis of the questionnaire data (evaluation after exercise)

VALKYRIES

EVALUATION OF THE UC4, Norway, 26-27 September 2023

UC4 after exercise feedback

Questionnaire for feedback survey with responders participating in the field exercise

Based on the feedback gathered from responders who participated in the joint Norway-Sweden-Denmark cross-border exercise in Norway on 26-27 September 2023, as part of the Valkyries project, the following findings and insights have been derived. The purpose of this questionnaire was to gather feedback and insights from participants, with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of the technological solutions and operational procedures.

17.1. Annex D1 – Exercise satisfactory

The UC4 exercise, which took place as part of the VALKYRIES project, underwent an evaluation process.

Respondents were presented with a questionnaire to evaluate the satisfaction with exercise. The first question gathered information about participants' prior experience with emergency response exercises. The subsequent questions, from Q2 to Q10, allowed respondents to rate various aspects of the exercise, such as preparation, training, scenario realism, coordination, logistics, timeline management, overall satisfaction, and knowledge gain from the exercise. Q11 focused on understanding the impact of the exercise on self-improvement, while Q12 encouraged respondents to provide narrative contributions, sharing their insights and suggestions for future exercises. The evaluation aimed to provide valuable feedback from participants, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement in UC4. This feedback will contribute to the continuous enhancement of the VALKYRIES project's exercises and methodologies.

Q1: Have you participated in or observed emergency response exercises or simulations in the past?

The majority of respondents (68%) reported having prior experience with emergency response exercises or simulations. Respondents with past experience can offer constructive feedback based on their comparisons, helping identify areas for improvement and enhancement in future exercises. The distribution of experience levels among participants in UC4's evaluation adds depth and diversity to the exercise evaluation process. It enables a more comprehensive assessment and helps tailor recommendations for improvement that consider both experienced and inexperienced perspectives.

Q2: How important is it to compare different emergency response scenarios and create common plans for conducting and reporting demonstrations

Greatly	82%
Considerably	14%
Moderate	0%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	4%

The responses indicate that a significant majority of participants find it highly important to compare different emergency response scenarios and create common plans for conducting and reporting demonstrations.

The strong agreement among participants regarding the importance of comparing different emergency response scenarios and creating common plans emphasized the exercise's relevance and alignment with their expectations. This alignment can enhance the effectiveness of the exercise in achieving its intended outcomes and promote ongoing enhancement in emergency response practices.

Q3: According to your opinion, was the selection of a full-scale type of exercise adequate for the demonstration of the proposed solutions?

Yes	89%
No	7%
N/A	4%

The responses considerably indicate a positive perception regarding the adequacy of selecting a full-scale type of exercise for demonstrating the proposed solutions. This positive responses may indicate that the exercise format was generally effective in showcasing the proposed solutions.

Q4: Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics)

Greatly	25%
Considerably	29%
Moderate	32%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	7%

The majority of participants expressed satisfaction with the exercise preparation. While there is a generally positive perception, there is also room for constructive feedback from participants who reported limited satisfaction. So, follow-up survey was conducted.

Q5: Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed solutions in the exercise.

Greatly	14%
Considerably	29%
Moderate	25%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	32%

While there is a presence of positive satisfaction responses, there is also a substantial proportion of N/A responses. This may be because the focus on training in UC4 wasn't as comprehensive as in other areas.

Q6: To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real-life emergency? Q7: How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?

Greatly	14%
Considerably	29%
Moderate	25%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	32%

The majority of participants (85%) found the scenario of UC4 to be realistic and responsive to a potentially real-life emergency. This indicates a high level of satisfaction with the realism of the scenario and suggests that UC4 effectively emulated the challenges and dynamics of a real-life emergency situation.

Q7: To what extent did the selected scenario showcase operational gaps in the response to a Multi-Casualty Incident and the added value that the proposed solutions bring in order to cover these gaps?

Greatly	7%
Considerably	46%
Moderate	36%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	11%

The majority of respondents recognized the scenario's effectiveness in showcasing operational gaps in the response to an MCI and demonstrating the potential value of proposed solutions. 36% of participants provided a moderate rating for this question. This information can be valuable for refining future exercises to more precisely address operational gaps and assess the impact of proposed solutions.

Q8: The extent, to which the objectives of the exercise i.e., effective exchange of information between different first responders and increased situational awareness for the agencies engaged in a MCI, are achieved.

Greatly	14%
Considerably	36%
Moderate	29%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	21%

These responses provide insight into the participants' perceptions of the exercise's effectiveness. The majority of participants felt the exercise successfully met its objectives, particularly in fostering effective information exchange and enhancing situational awareness.

Q9: How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?

Greatly	14%
Considerably	43%
Moderate	36%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	7%

The majority of participants viewed the coordination of the exercise positively in terms of promoting effective collaboration among participants.

Q10: How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?

Greatly	36%
Considerably	25%
Moderate	32%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	7%

A significant portion of participants had positive views, some viewed the logistics more moderately. This indicates that they likely found the logistics satisfactory but may have seen room for enhancement.

Q11: The extent, to which the timeline of the exercise was appropriately managed and followed the pre-defined schedule.

Greatly	7%
Considerably	32%
Moderate	54%
Limited	4%
Not at all	0%
N/A	4%

A majority of respondents, accounting for 54%, chose 'Moderate.' This suggests that participants viewed the management of the exercise timeline as moderately effective, reflecting an overall satisfactory handling despite minor unforeseen incidents. For instance, the schedule experienced a minor setback when the bus driver had difficulty locating the place in the morning, and there was a delay when the observer boat was grounded after the exercise. These incidents, while contributing to deviations from the schedule, provided valuable learning experiences and highlighted the need for adaptability in real-world emergency response scenarios. Overall, the incidents were efficiently managed, ensuring the exercise continued smoothly, thereby affirming the participants' general satisfaction with the timeline management.

Q12: Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?

Greatly	21%
Considerably	43%
Moderate	14%
Limited	18%
Not at all	0%
N/A	4%

The responses indicate a range of satisfaction levels with the conduct of the exercise. While the majority found it satisfactory, there were participants who expressed reservations, pointing out specific areas that impacted their experience (additional feedback from follow-up survey). This additional feedback provided more detailed insights. The results of the follow-up survey will be discussed in further detail later in Annex D2.

Q13: Your participation in the exercise, the implementation of tools and interaction with other stakeholders allowed you to increase your knowledge on innovative solutions and newly proposed methodologies that can be of added value for your operational work.

Greatly	21%
Considerably	43%
Moderate	14%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	14%

The responses indicate a generally positive perception of the exercise's role in increasing participants' knowledge of innovative solutions and methodologies. The majority found it to be considerably valuable in this regard.

Q14: Please, indicate strengths and also areas that require improvement, to be considered for future exercises.

The strengths of the exercise include an improved understanding among participants, effective planning, realism, and overall positive perceptions. However, while aspects of communication were effective and contributed to these strengths, there were also areas within communication that need enhancement, such as ensuring consistency across various stages or utilizing more reliable technology. Other areas for improvement include providing clearer exercise objectives, addressing logistical challenges, and further refining observation and information-sharing methods. These insights can guide future exercise planning and execution to better meet participant expectations and improve upon areas that showed both strength and potential for growth.

17.2. Annex D2 – Opportunities

The UC4 within the VALKYRIES project presented a opportunity to evaluate and assess predefined opportunities aimed at enhancing various aspects of emergency response. These opportunities were designed to improve critical functions, including location tracking, cross-border data traceability, digitalization impact on voice communication, wearable technology for triage support, utilization of data from harmonization tasks for learning, and logistics assistance through UAVs.

In Valkyries, there are four different Use Cases, with an aim to maintain consistency by using a similar questionnaire for feedback in each case. However, UC4 had some distinct aspects that made some of the questions less applicable or relevant to participants. As a result, we received more “N/A” responses compared to the other Use Cases. This doesn’t mean the feedback from UC4 is less valuable. It reflects the specific nature of that scenario. All feedback received, including the “N/A” responses, is appreciated as it helps us understand the unique challenges and perspectives of UC4.

Q15: Regarding Location Tracking, to what extent did harmonization efforts successfully improve the tracking of vehicles locations during exercise?

Greatly	7%
Considerably	36%
Moderate	21%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	29%

While harmonization efforts led to notable improvements in location tracking, the feedback, particularly from the follow-up survey, emphasizes the necessity to address the operational challenges of new technologies. For instance, Tap2SOS bracelets encountered connectivity problems, sometimes necessitating the removal of phone casings, which could delay emergency responders' access to crucial location information.

Q16: Regarding cross border data trace, to what extent did the exercise improve information sharing and data traceability among responding organizations?

Greatly	7%
Considerably	25%
Moderate	14%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	46%

Q17: Regarding digitalization Impact on Voice Communication, how much did the digitalization actions reduce the need for voice communication by transferring information digitally?

Greatly	7%
Considerably	21%
Moderate	18%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	46%

Q18: Regarding use of wearable to support triage, did the use of the wearable bracelet with specific medical data facilitate triage and reduce risks for the victims

Greatly	7%
Considerably	18%
Moderate	18%
Limited	14%
Not at all	0%
N/A	43%

Among those who did respond, there is a range of opinions. Some participants noted that the use of wearable bracelets with specific medical data considerably or moderately facilitated triage and reduced risks for victims. However, a notable percentage also indicated limited effectiveness in this regard. Additional feedback indicates that the reason respondents hold this view is due to the unstable connection in maritime environments.

Q19: Regarding utilizing data from the Harmonization tasks for Learning, how valuable is the data from harmonization tasks for learning and improving future emergency response actions

Greatly	14%
Considerably	36%
Moderate	11%
Limited	0%
Not at all	0%
N/A	39%

Among those who did provide feedback, there is an appreciable level of positive sentiment. Participants noted that the data from harmonization tasks had been greatly or considerably valuable for learning and enhancing future emergency response actions.

Q20: Regarding logistics assistance using UAVs, how much did the use of drones expedite equipment transportation between first responder teams.

Greatly	11%
Considerably	36%
Moderate	18%
Limited	7%
Not at all	0%
N/A	29%

A notable portion of respondents found the use of drones to be considerably valuable (36%) in expediting equipment transportation between first responder teams. Additionally, 18% of respondents rated it as moderately effective in this regard.

17.3. Annex D3 – Follow-up Survey

After the initial offline survey, a follow-up online survey was conducted to further explore participants' experiences, perspectives, and suggestions regarding the UC4. This online survey aimed to provide a more comprehensive assessment of participant satisfaction and to pinpoint specific areas for improvement. The online survey included five open-ended questions. These questions invited participants to provide more detailed and qualitative feedback.

Follow-up Q1: What aspects of UC4 did you find most effective or successful?

Participants appreciated several effective aspects of UC4. They appreciated that UC4 aimed to avoid simulation, making it more realistic and allowing them to discover more issues. In addition, UC4 provided an opportunity to experiment with innovative solutions for challenging emergency situations at sea, which participants found effective. The successful drone-aided rescue of a civilian at sea was considered one of best aspects. The visualization of incidents on the platform (GlobalCOP) was also mentioned as an effective component of UC4.

Follow-up Q2: Were there any specific challenges or issues you encountered during UC4?

While some participants did not encounter any specific challenges or issues, others highlighted various difficulties:

- Some participants expressed the need to see more cross-border communication and coordination during the exercise
- Issues related to communication tools, such as the need for tablets or smartphones for first responders, were mentioned.
- The complexity of implementing new technologies and proposed solutions was recognized as a challenge, which helped identify weaknesses for future scenarios.
- The observer boat was grounded at the end of exercise, but the incidents were managed efficiently
- Some participants found it challenging to view triage and other activities due to the distance from the observers' boat.

Follow-up Q3: How would you rate the effectiveness of communication and collaboration among participants and teams during UC4?

Feedback on communication and collaboration varied:

- Some participants reported problems with live streams from body cameras and drones, suggesting technical challenges.
- The need for more cross-border involvement and commitment
- The potential for more realistic training before exercises

Follow-up Q4: Did the technological tools (drone, body cam) and Valkyries solutions (GlobalCOP, TASSICA Triage Card, Tab2SOS) used in UC4 meet your expectations? If not, please specify areas for improvement.

Participants provided mixed feedback on the technological tools and Valkyries solutions:

- Drone and Body Cam Challenges: Drone and body cam functionality was noted as problematic, particularly in terms of not receiving images.
- Positive GlobalCOP Feedback: GlobalCOP was commended as a valuable solution for first responders to track actions within MCIs.
- TASSICA Triage Cards: TASSICA Triage Cards were considered effective but were noted to have limitations under "ideal conditions" without water or rain.
- Tab2SOS Connectivity: Connectivity issues with Tab2SOS bracelets were reported, including the need to remove phone casings for connectivity.
- Tool Descriptions: Some participants indicated a need for more specific descriptions of the tools.

Follow-up Q5: Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience in UC4?

Participants shared additional thoughts on their UC4 experience:

- Observer Groups: Suggestions were made to divide observers into different groups, some on boats and others onshore, to improve visibility.
- Importance of Preparedness: Despite difficulties, participants recognized the importance of emergency preparedness and technology use.
- Exercise Script and Adaptation: Some participants desired longer explanations of exercise scripts and better adaptation of Valkyries tools for maritime environments.
- Clearer Collaboration: Clearer collaboration and harmonization across countries were recommended.

Overall, the feedback from participants provides valuable insights into the strengths and areas for improvement in UC4, which can inform future emergency response exercises and the optimization of innovative solutions in maritime environments.

18. Annex E – Evidence

18.1. Screenshots of the Applications for UC4

Figure 27 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 Global view of all incidents

Name	Type	Location	Organisation
University of South-Eastern Norway	Government	LMZLN 214446, 10.8171	
USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 222092, 10.8400	University of South-Eastern Norway
Swedish Coast Guard	Government	LutLon 220043, 11.1700	
Swedish Coast Guard-Steinsholm	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 214168, 11.1404	Swedish Coast Guard
Other organisations	Government	LMZLN 229631, 10.7451	
OTHOrg Miscellaneous vessels unit	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 220031, 10.7481	Other organisations
The Norwegian Sea Rescue Society	Government	LutLon 214168, 11.1404	
RS Rostvæn	Public safety, emergency point	LMZLN 214416, 10.8151	The Norwegian Sea Rescue Society
Norwegian Coast Guard	Government	LutLon 220040, 10.8190	
Coast Guard Mobile Command Post	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 220252, 10.4088	Norwegian Coast Guard
Horten Coast Guard Base	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 214241, 10.4844	Norwegian Coast Guard
Norwegian Coastal Administration	Government	LutLon 220150, 10.1511	
Norwegian Coastal Administration-Other	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 220252, 10.4088	Norwegian Coastal Administration
Norwegian Coastal Administration-Horten	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 214241, 10.4844	Norwegian Coastal Administration
NCA FORWARD CENTER POST	Public safety, emergency point	LMZLN 214114, 10.8144	Norwegian Coastal Administration
HRS South Norway	Government	LutLon 220081, 10.0000	
HRS South Norway unit 1	Public safety, emergency point	LutLon 220002, 10.0000	HRS South Norway
DOO	Government	LutLon 214168, 11.1404	
Danish Coast Guard Skagen	Public safety, emergency point	LMZLN 220150, 10.9840	DOO

Figure 28 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 Detailed view of all participating organisations

Staff / Asset	Type	Status	Location	Organization	Unit	Destination	ETO
Wesert 918	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104701	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Isak 918	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104701	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Marcus 917	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104401	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Per 916	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Leif 915	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Dag Erik 914	Critical Intervention Specialist	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Jon 912	Critical Intervention Specialist	Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104401	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Gisle 912	Critical Intervention Specialist	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104401	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
Fabio 911	Rotary Pilot	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
USN Drone	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104401, 104404	University of South-Eastern Norway	USN Miscellaneous vehicles unit		
KDK Hans-Erik 011	Emergency Vehicle Operator - (Drone)	Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	Swedish Coast Guard	Swedish Coast Guard-Strömstad		
Sten Erik 010	Emergency Vehicle Operator - (Drone)	Not Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104404	Swedish Coast Guard	Swedish Coast Guard-Strömstad		
KSV 010	Coast Guard Search and Rescue	Not Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104404	Swedish Coast Guard	Swedish Coast Guard-Strömstad		
KSV 002	Coast Guard Search and Rescue	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	Swedish Coast Guard	Swedish Coast Guard-Strömstad		
Ullagutt	Coast Guard/Over Water Body Rescue Team	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	Other organizations	OSN (Swedish Coast Guard)		
Erik	Tug Boat/General	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	Other organizations	OSN (Swedish Coast Guard)		
Tillett	Tug Boat/General	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104404	Other organizations	OSN (Swedish Coast Guard)		
Tugboat Peter	Tug Boat/General	Not Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104404	Other organizations	OSN (Swedish Coast Guard)		
Myllengen	Tug Boat/General	Not Available	UM, OS (W 404) 104404	Other organizations	OSN (Swedish Coast Guard)		
Fabio Alcortano Andreia	Rotary Pilot	Not Available	Luf, OS (W 404) 104401	The Norwegian Sea Rescue Society	OS Helicopter		

Figure 29 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: Example of the UC4 assets and staff list status and their location

Figure 30 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 global view of the assets (ships and vehicles)

Figure 31 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 Details of a participation ship

Figure 32 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 global view of victims’ transportation status and global figures

Figure 33 – Annex E: GLOBAL_COP: UC4 global view of victims’ triage status, Destination, assigned transportation

18.2. Photos from UC4

Figure 34 – Annex E: victim on the shore

Figure 35 – Annex E: Observers boat

Figure 36 – Annex E: Rescuing a victim 1

Figure 37 – Annex E: Rescuing a victim 2

Figure 38 – Annex E: Drone operation